

ROLE OF WOMEN IN NATION BUILDING AND DEVELOPMENT

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Introduction

"Woman" is the best and unsurpassed creator of the Creator. Measuring the beauty of the woman and the height of the serpent and its depth is not only difficult but it is impossible. In the social, cultural, religious, geographical, historical and literary world, there is also a revelation of the diverse forms of women, not only the external, but the dysfunctional nature of interpersonal interaction. Woman, nature, and God is a wonderful "holy sacrifice" given by God, which is necessary to realize 'holy instrument'. There is no border or no end to it! This is a vast form, in front of which the creator himself is also a knit. This is 'Amrit-Varadaan' as well as 'Divine medicine'. Woman is the smell of the mud of the soil, which carries the life-style and plays an important role in not only personal but national-creation and development. For women it should be said that this - "There is unity in diversity" ... then there will be no exaggeration. Because there is variety in women's outer form, beauty and dress, but in their mind there is 'Ekam' like monotony and central power God. Around the same power, many types of virtues like the Sun and other planets are constantly moving, such as faith, love, compassion, loyalty, compassion, dedication, sacrifice, sacrifice, compassion, coolness, affection, efficiency, dutifulness, tolerance, Limit, equality, creativity and tolerance etc. -As a result of these many powers, there is wonderful and unparalleled contribution of women's nation-building and development. We can understand this continuous contribution of women through some points –

1. Contributions as a mother:

Having regard to the spirit, duty, creativity and love of human welfare as paramount, women have taken their special responsibilities in nation-building and development while playing their paramount role in the form of a mother in this world. By giving birth to children, raising them to the highest development of virtues and virtues and ensuring their responsibility towards the nation so that nation building and development will continue without any movement. The incarnation of Vaibhav Bhagat Singh, Chandrasekhar, Vivekananda, in the countryside, is the nature of the "Mother". The sacrifice, dedication and sacrifice of many mothers like Mata Jijabai, Jaywantabai, Penhadayhai are still on the golden pages of history. Mother is the one who builds and develops multi-dimensional personality, which is essential for nation-building. Napoleon Bonaparte had said, considering the dignity of "mother" - give me a worthy mother, I will give you a worthy nation. From this statement, there is hidden contribution of the nature of the nation in the formation and development of the nation.

2. Contribution to the wife: -

After the mother, the avatar of the wife plays a significant role in the nation-building and development. Wife wants to make her husband virtuous and virtuous. It has been seen for centuries that whenever a crisis has happened on the country, wives have sent tilak on their forehead and sent them with zeal, passion and faith in the battlefield. Not only this, the wife has become a "hadi" by cutting the sheesh. Literature is a reflection of society Which contributes to nation-building and development. This contribution can be seen as a significant contribution of wives. For example - To give spiritual consciousness to the life of Tulsidas, his wife was "intellectually clever" of Ratnavali. "Vidyutma" had created Kalidas as the great poet of Sanskrit. If we mention the little thing, it will not be unreasonable that the husband keeps the

wife away from the evils of corruption, dishonesty, robbery, embezzlement, etc., which makes the nation hollow, which is for the development of the country's economy. It is also right.

3. Contributions in the form of a housewife:

In the Indian society, women are the main "axis" of the family, which play a great role in nation-building and development as a housewife, which is embellished and beautified by the beauty of "Annapurna" Is there. As a housewife, he operates the whole family smoothly and also develops the trend of saving for the family's operation. All the countries were aggrieved by the global economic downturn in the year 1930, 1998, 2008 and 2014, but not India!!! Why the nature of saving of Indian women saved the Indian economy. The same example we got to see during the note-taking of the year 2016. At the same time, about 65 percent of women work in agriculture and animal husbandry and promote the development of the country's economy. In addition to creating handicrafts, they accelerate development work. Therefore, this is also a part of nation-building and development.

4. Contribution to the culture, rites and preserves of traditions: - Women are the real custodians of culture, rites and traditions. They continue to transmit and protect them from generation to generation; women have been the role of women in the world for achieving world class status. That is why India is called a country of culture and traditions.

5. Social-educational-religious contributions: -

Civilization, culture, rites and traditions are transferred to one generation from generation to generation due to women. Thus, the socio-educational-religious work of women empowers the individual, the family, the society and the nation. It has also been said that a strong woman is the cornerstone of a strong society. Mother is the first teacher of the child, who is responsible for the overall development of the child. When this teacher leaves the family and

provides education in society, then it becomes a best and clean work. The country's first teacher "Savitri Bai Phule" is an exemplary example. Maitreya, Gargi, Vishwara, Lopamudra, Ghosha and Vidushi of Vedic civilization are still auspicious to contribute to the field of education, which have made unprecedented contribution to nation-building and development.

6. Contribution to the Freedom Movement:

Slavery is not only obstacle in nation-building and development, but it provides stability to the nation. This is the reason that women in the Indian independence movement made sure to take part in their partnership and make new India. In our freedom movement, many women gave their invaluable contributions and gave their best wishes. Captain Lakshmi Sehgal, Aruna Asaf Ali, Durga Bhabhi, Madam Bhikaji Kanma, Sarojini Naidu and Annie Besant have given their incomparable contributions to nation-building and development.

7. Scientific contributions:

The area of scientific research and research is not insulated for women due to self-confidence, passion, hard work, hard work, creativity and intellectual skills. Today many women are contributing in the form of defence experts and scientists in nation-building and development. Dr. Tecsey Thomas has won the honour of "India's Missile Woman and Agniputri", representing the Agni-5 missile plan. Many such women are contributing to nation-building and development while ensuring their participation in scientific development.

8. Political Contribution:

The direction and condition of the country's politics depends on the fact that what is the person conducting them? In this sequence, women have proved that they can fulfil their participation in political development. Sarojini Naidu, Sucheta Kripalani, Indira Gandhi etc. have used their political talent in nation-building and development, which is an important and meaningful step.

9. Contribution to the administrative area

Administration of any nation is indicative of the progress and development of that nation. If the administrative efficiency and skill are convinced then the progress and development of the nation is certain. At present, many women are giving their incomparable contribution to nation-building and development by ensuring their presence in the Indian Administrative Service and State Administrative Services.

10. Literary contribution:

Mirror of literature, society is done. Through the literature, nation-building and development can be done at the highest level, because literature can not only be fully developed of intellectual skills or personality. If this literary-work is done by women, it is auspicious on gold, because the existing "Marm" in women makes literature quality. Many women have contributed a lot to the nation-building and development through literature-creationism, such as Mahadevi Verma, Amrita Pritam, Meera, Ashapura Devi, Mahasweta Devi, Jhumpa Lahiri and Subhadra Kumari Chauhan etc. He wrote such a classical literature, which emphasizes personality development as well as spiritual and moral development, in which the voices of consciousness and nation-building are highlighted.

Therefore, we can say that women have made their unprecedented contribution in nation-building and development through their duties, skills and creativity. Even today, women are well educated, competent, and successful as men, whether it is social, economic, political, religious, sports, art, literature, history, geography, astronomy, medicine, service, media or journalism. Women's presence, contribution, qualifications, achievements, poignancy and creativity give a direct introduction to themselves. Handling the family and society, at the national and international level, women have always made their special and unprecedented contribution to nation-

building and development by waving the victory. This is the reason that he is also "Self-Siddha", along with creation, Annapurna, Goddess, era-era and ego-creation.

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